

Response of salt-tolerant rice somaclones to different levels of nitrogen

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Breeding for and subsequent cultivation of tolerant varieties have proved effective in harnessing limiting ecosystems worldwide, which otherwise remain idle. In the humid tropics of Bay islands, about 4,000 ha in valleys remain fallow due to frequent inundation with tidal sea water. Our earlier attempts to cultivate conventionally bred salt-tolerant rice varieties in those areas were only partially successful due to the inherent low yield of available varieties. The potential of in vitro culture-induced variation (somaclonal variation) was explored in developing salt-tolerant rice varieties suitable for such areas. Nine promising somaclones derived from a tall traditional salt-tolerant cultivar Pokkali (Mandal et al 1999) were assessed for their response to different N doses in the wet tropics of Andaman islands. The major objective was to select the most suitable among the somaclones and to determine the optimum level of N requirement to attain maximum yield.

The experiment was conducted under rainfed conditions at the Field Crops Research Station of CARI, Port Blair (lat 11° 41' 13.04" N; long 92° 43' 30.16" E), in a split-plot design with three replications during the wet seasons of 1997 and 1998. Nine semidwarf somaclones, with parents Pokkali and a modern high-yielding variety (HYV)—Taichung Sen Yu—as check, formed the main plot (Table 1). Four levels of N (0, 40, 80, 120 kg ha⁻¹) were used in the subplot (plot size 4 m × 3 m). Selected somaclones were originally developed from 1,190 primary regenerants by recurrent selection for seven generations under saline and normal soils. The soil of the experimental plot—a typical salt soil of the area—was clay loam in texture, with a pH of 6.8 containing 142 kg ha⁻¹ alkaline permanganate extractable available N (low level), 16 kg Olsen P ha⁻¹ (medium level), and 182 kg NH₄OAc-extractable K ha⁻¹ (me-

dium level). Based on the yield of each entry at different N levels pooled over years, quadratic response functions were fitted. Using these functions, the optimum N levels as well as the agronomic N use efficiency at optimum N levels were determined for each of the somaclones.

The somaclones displayed significant variation in yield and yield-attributing characters. Five out of nine somaclones were significantly taller, whereas others were on a par with the check variety. Taichung Sen Yu produced the most tillers per plant and was on a par with BTS16. Tiller number per plant of all other somaclones varied between 10 and 12. BTS24 showed the highest number of

panicles per plant. Panicle length did not vary much among the somaclones. All somaclones except BTS2 outyielded the check (Table 1). BTS24 had the highest yield, which was on a par with BTS18, BTS13, and BTS17. The average yield of all somaclones pooled over years was significantly higher than that of Taichung Sen Yu, except for BTS11-11, BTS11-3-1, and BTS2. On average, the somaclones produced 18.5% higher yield than the check, with a maximum of 30% for BTS24. The harvest index (HI) of the somaclones, ranging from 33.0% to 37.5%, was also better than the check's (30.8%), except for BTS11-3-1, BTS11-16, and BTS11-11.

Table 1. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of salt-tolerant Pokkali somaclones at different N levels.

Somaclone	N level (kg ha ⁻¹)				Mean ^a
	0	40	80	120	
<i>1996-97</i>					
BTS17	3.1	4.0	4.4	4.3	4.0 a
BTS18	3.2	3.9	4.4	4.3	4.0 a
BTS2	2.6	3.2	3.4	3.3	3.1
BTS24	3.5	4.3	4.5	4.3	4.2 a
BTS11-3-1	2.4	3.2	3.8	3.6	3.3
BTS11-16	2.3	3.3	3.9	3.5	3.2
BTS13	3.3	4.0	4.3	4.2	3.9 a
BTS11-11	2.6	3.2	3.4	3.3	3.1
BTS16	2.6	3.6	4.2	4.0	3.6
Pokkali (parent)	1.9	2.4	2.6	2.3	2.3
Taichung Sen Yu (HYV check)	2.6	3.2	3.4	3.2	3.1
Mean	2.7	3.5	4.2 a	4.0 a	
CD (P = 0.05)	Variety = 0.26, Nitrogen = 0.32, V × N = not significant				
<i>1997-98</i>					
BTS17	3.4	4.2	4.6	4.6	4.2 a
BTS18	3.4	4.2	4.7	4.6	4.2 a
BTS2	2.6	3.4	3.6	3.4	3.2
BTS24	3.4	4.3	4.8	4.7	4.3 a
BTS11-3-1	2.6	3.4	3.9	3.6	3.4
BTS11-16	2.8	3.6	4.0	4.0	3.6
BTS13	3.4	4.2	4.5	4.4	4.1 a
BTS11-11	2.8	3.6	4.0	3.7	3.5
BTS16	3.0	3.6	4.2	4.2	3.7
Pokkali (parent)	1.8	2.3	2.6	2.3	2.3
Taichung Sen Yu (HYV check)	3.0	3.6	4.0	3.9	3.6
Mean	2.9	3.7	4.1 a	4.0 a	
CD (P = 0.05)	Variety = 0.20, Nitrogen = 0.25, V × N = not significant				

^aa = denotes statistical parity among treatments.

The yield of somaclones peaked at 80 kg N ha⁻¹ but declined beyond 80 kg ha⁻¹. The calculated optimum level of N for the somaclones varied between 63 and 75 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 2). The calculated maximum agronomic N-use efficiency was for BTS24 (10.6 kg ha⁻¹ kg⁻¹ N), followed by BTS18, BTS13, and BTS11-16. Vigorous crop growth seemed to be governed by a large number of tillers and higher yield-attributing characters. The

highest yield of BTS24 at all N levels probably resulted in higher agronomic N-use efficiency compared with other somaclones (Table 1). This line also showed a more distinct quadratic response function compared with other lines (Table 2).

In summary, 63–70 kg N ha⁻¹ seems to be the optimum range to obtain maximum yields of Pokkali somaclones in the wet tropics of the Andamans. BTS24 was

the most promising somaclone, outyielding the check Taichung Sen Yu. BTS24 may be cultivated on a large scale in the Andamans and tested elsewhere under similar agronomic environments.

Reference

Mandal AB, Pramanik SC, Choudhury B, Bandyopadhyay AK. 1999. Salt-tolerant somaclones: performance under normal saline soils in Bay Islands. *Field Crops Res.* 61:13–21.

Table 2. Response function of Pokkali somaclones at different N levels.

Somaclone	Response function ^a	R ^{2b}	Optimum N level (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield at optimum N level (t ha ⁻¹)	Agronomic N-use efficiency
BTS17	$Y = 3,284 + 10.45 X - 0.024 x^2$	0.778*	66.4	3.9	8.86
BTS18	$Y = 3,145 + 11.34 X - 0.027 x^2$	0.885*	69.7	3.8	9.45
BTS2	$Y = 2,463 + 9.14 X - 0.019 x^2$	0.739*	63.7	3.0	7.90
BTS24	$Y = 3,326 + 11.74 X - 0.015 x^2$	0.757*	75.4	4.1	10.60
BTS11-3-1	$Y = 2,346 + 9.75 X - 0.021 x^2$	0.802*	64.0	2.9	8.40
BTS11-16	$Y = 2,472 + 10.42 X - 0.015 x^2$	0.833*	62.7	3.1	9.48
BTS13	$Y = 3,147 + 10.57 X - 0.014 x^2$	0.752*	71.6	3.8	9.57
BTS11-11	$Y = 2,446 + 9.65 X - 0.018 x^2$	0.789*	65.7	3.0	8.47
BTS16	$Y = 2,437 + 10.15 X - 0.021 x^2$	0.872*	70.0	3.0	8.68
Pokkali (parent)	$Y = 2,026 + 1.77 X - 0.018 x^2$	0.778*	52.4	2.1	9.54
Taichung Sen Yu (HYV check)	$Y = 2,365 + 9.72 X - 0.024 x^2$	0.801*	63.6	2.9	8.19

^aY = yield in kg ha⁻¹, X = N level in kg ha⁻¹. ^b** = significant at P = 0.05.

Information support system for rice crop management

TropRice is an information support system of best-bet practices designed to provide practical field-level guides for rice crop management in the tropics. It aims to help users make informed decisions related to rice production.

It is not a single system for the world. It contains some generic information, but some are site- or region-specific. TropRice is intended to be a template that could be modified for different environments. As improved systems on component technologies become available, they will replace or be linked to the system. The present system is aimed at irrigated rice in a Los Baños, Philippines-type of environment.

TropRice is an ongoing project developed by IRRI scientists and specialists who have contributed to the technical content. It is intended for intermediary technology transfer agents as a response to the recognition that many farmers do not have access to information on how to grow rice. Current information technology offers new ways of packaging and presenting information. The system is being evaluated among three separate groups: nongovernment organizations, farmers, and the private and public sector.

Web site: <http://www.cgiar.org/irri/TropRice>

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